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DISC2023

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Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

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TRICLOSAN IN ANTIBACTERIAL PRODUCTS ON THE SERBIAN MARKET – HEALTH RISKS AND REGULATORY IMPLICATIONS

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Abstract: Triclosan (TCS) is a synthetic antimicrobial agent used in various personal care products (PCPs), such as toothpaste, mouthwashes, soaps, disinfectants, and anti-acne preparations. Given the potential endocrine-disruptive effects, the use of TCS in certain FDA-regulated antiseptic products has been banned since 2016. However, in healthcare settings, TCS is still in use, putting healthcare workers at an increased risk of exposure, especially following the COVID-19 outbreak and stringent hygiene protocols. On the contrary, the European Commission restricted its use as a biocide but is still allowing its application in PCPs. The aim of this research was to examine the presence of TCS in PCPs available on the Serbian market by analysing product declarations. The sampling of PCPs was conducted in drugstores and pharmacy chains, including their online stores. The 184 PCPs in the Serbian market met the selection criteria. Based on the obtained results, 9 out of 184 products (4.9%) contained TCS. The TCS-containing products included toothpaste, mouthwashes, hand disinfectants, and anti-acne products. The number of PCPs with TCS declared on the Serbian market is lower in comparison with bigger markets, such as the US, where at least 479 OTC FDA-labelled products contain TCS. Despite the decreased use of TCS globally, TCS remains a high-production volume chemical. Based on the international biomonitoring data, TCS urinary concentrations were in the range of 2.6 – 12468 nM, probably due to its bioaccumulation potential. Furthermore, high urinary TCS concentrations were associated with infertility, diabetes, thyroid impairment, and other endocrine-related disorders. The awareness within the scientific community and regulatory bodies regarding the negative effects of TCS has influenced its presence on the market. However, while the FDA has prohibited the use of TCS in certain products, it can be still found in some PCPs, emphasising the need for continued scrutiny and harmonised regulations to mitigate associated health risks.

Keywords: *Triclosan; Endocrine Disruptors; Personal Care Products; Market Analysis.*

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